
Television Advertising and Its Impact on Children

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Abstract

Advertising is a form of communication that is done to influence the sale of a service, product or commodity, to promote or propagate a thought, or to bring about any other change desired by those financing or executing the advertisement or commercial. Advertising tends to have the strongest influence on children, who are considered the most susceptible target group. With impressionable minds, they tend to retain the message of advertisements more lucidly and without judgment. Furthermore, they tend to spend more time watching television and also have limited exposure to the outside world as opposed to adults. Therefore, the onus lies with parents to regulate the content that is available and accessible to children. Such content moderation must be done in accordance with societal norms and the teachings of Islam. This paper explores the potential impact of advertising on children in Pakistani society, with special emphasis in the context of Islamic teachings. As a religion, Islam provides a comprehensive code of ethics for raising children. This study analyzes a sample of commercials that have been developed for children through a survey to determine its effects on the intended audience.

Keywords: Television, Advertisement, Children, Behavior, Attitudes, Consumer Buying.

Introduction

Advertising means incurring a cost to use a medium of communication for the propagation of an idea, a product or a service. It can use one of several mediums including print, broadcast, digital, film, television, etc. The purpose can vary from creating awareness to a call of action; an explanation or a promotion. The American Market Association defined advertising as: "Any paid form of non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods or services by an identified sponsor" (Jefkins, 1987)

It has one clear difference from publicity where there can be questions over its purpose and the source of sponsorship. In advertising, the source is almost always clearly identified.

It also differs from personal selling because it is done through a medium and not through an individual in a personal capacity. It is also wrong to equate advertising with sales promotion.

Sales promotion constitutes a gamut of activities and includes advertisement, personal selling and others such as above-the-line and below-the-line selling, kiosks and give-aways, exhibitions and displays etc.

Therefore, it would be correct to say that advertising is an aspect of the wholesome activity of sales promotion.

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It is also the time-tested tool for shaping and changing perceptions. It targets the mind through a variety of visual, textual, aural and subliminal cues.

The Institute of the Practitioner in Advertising (British) gives advertising a proficient and reliable role and brings out market research, inventive and media effect services and professionalism of the advertising organization.

The greatest extension of television as a medium accrued after the primary programs was broadcast in 1941. Following World War II, the use of television advertising grew swiftly. In 1955 colour television was used. Today television has become the second largest advertising medium (after newspapers) in terms of total dollars used up by advertisers. (Garbner, 1999). In the present time, television advertising, has hastily established its extraordinary supremacy. Indeed so excited were many national advertisers to coin in on this exclusive of attainment and persuading mass audiences, specially youth, that felines were swiftly abstracted to the medium, foremost to complain that television contractors had been gifted a certificate to print money; Since expensive familiarity, the worth of commercial television had been proved accurate time and again the numerous campaigns both national and locally.

Management techniques too, have sophisticated over the years, while the higher standards of portrait explanation and the forward of colour have enhanced the medium's potential almost ahead of contrast with those revolutionary days of anticipation, experimentation and wonders. (Sills, 1991, pp 5-8) The basic objective of all advertisements is that message should reach the desired target. The message needs some communication carrier. These vehicles of communication are called advertising media.

BACKGROUND

Man has come a long way since the days of the hunter-gatherer. But even in primitive societies, people were dependent upon each other for basic survival. The prevalence of barter trade demonstrates importance of communication.

Advertising and marketing have been part of human history and evolved side by side to reach the point they have in today's inter-dependence and connectivity.

Though the term advertising appears a new and innovative, but this communication mode existed when Allah All Mighty sent Adam and Eve on earth tasked to spread God's message to the people. Allah sent messengers (124,000 prophets) and four books containing his message through chosen prophets.

As the society started developing and people started coming closer to each other their reliance on each other has become a way of life to cater to the needs of their day to day life. People became dependent on each other for their needs whether someone wants to sell something or buy. Sellers and buyers sent out their needs through word of mouth among their acquaintances, friends circle etc. This way the message of a particular person reached/conveyed to the persons at various levels in the society. This is how one person was able to sell his product or services. (P ant, 2007, pp 6-7).

There are also signs suggesting that the Ancient Civilizations were cognizant of the importance of advertising. It was confirmed by Areebeoligists working in the countries near Mediterranean Sea and they found symbols publicising various events and offers. Such

announcements were found about goods for sale dated back to the 3000 BC and 1000 BC. Greeks relied on messages conveyed to them by town and cities criers. This system was used in several European countries. The criers were also joined/accompanied by musicians or the traders who could hire a person who could work as criers for them, or the junior of the magistrate would inform the public on behalf of the magistrate. The essential purpose of town criers was to draw the public attention/concentration about the announcement to the public and society. These town criers acted as the medium for the community announcement. During the golden age, in Greece municipality town criers announced the sale of livestock, crafted item also cosmetics and makeup items etc. (Pant, 2007, pp 13-15).

During the ancient times, the Romans also painted walls in order to inform people and declare gladiator fights. The Phoenicians were known to paint factures that promoted wars on huge rocks along their march past routes. In the skeletons of Pompeii, archaeologists found a painting showing praising a politician and asking for votes. Signs and symbols were also used by the shopkeepers on the shops showing what the shops were selling. In the anoint days most of the advertisement were based on special events i.e. unexpected happening such as when a child was lost, an escaped slave, or the order of the king for the public (Wirnmer and Dominick, 1994, Pp 5-6).

In the early days word "advertising" was not intended to be meant as we know it today. In fact it was differing that of what it means today and was often used to advertise some product and service. It was linked to individual's profit.

Those lived in ancient period, be in Egypt, Rome or Greece, undoubtedly must have heard and responded to the shouts of street vendors. Generally it was believed that the ancient age advertisement would have been probably shouts of those town criers marking location of shops or spots for the target population of the town. The most significant event in the history of advertising was the invention of moveable type by Johannes Gutenberg in 1440. (Mandell, l, Maurica; Advertising; pp 18-20).

It was in 1650 when the first newspaper advertisement appeared on the back page of a London newspaper that offered reward money for the return of twelve houses. As the time passed the use of advertisements to sell products like chocolate, medicine, real estate, utensils, coffee etc was started. When the radio was introduced television, newspapers and magazines were forced to compete with electronic media. Radio was available in the market in 1920 and soon after this television surfaced on the scene using words supported by pictures to promote products. With this development the advertisement relied on spoken words and moving pictures as well as written words to accomplish its objectives. (Mandell, ins Pp 26-27).

Experience of decades (historically) proved that the advertising is the most effective and efficient method of introducing the new or improved product and services in the market in order to register the products/services in the mind of the people who are recipient of the message and consumers of the product and services so advertised. Such a role of the advertising is also acknowledged for it contribution in the economy of the country. It is a general belief that advertising that sells products and ideas, brings about changes in behaviour, influence, and has impact on the attitude of the people.

Despite advertising's impact and role in business/economy and bringing change in the

attitude of the people some strongly believe that people are immune to advertising influences. Jeffrey Schrant put this assertion by saying: "The personality immune consider most advertisement dumb, silly beneath my dignity and generally a waste of time". Members of this group can sometimes be heard to say "Ads seldom influence my opinion. I am an informed consumer who knows true value when I see it".

Yet, advertisement, this group believes, are evidently aimed at those unfortunate (People)... who rush out and purchase promiscuously. Strongly enough, 90 percent accounts for approximately 90 percent of all purchases of advertised products... obviously something is amiss". (Baker Stephen; 1990 p, p 102).

However, as John O Toole Said" In reality advertising is not about products, but about a person and his (her) life... and how the products can fit into that life to make it easier, richer or more rewarding". (Moslow, Abraham, P 14, 1990). In other words one can say that advertising help to influence consumer behaviour.

RELATED STUDIES

Now it is evident that advertising in 21st century would not be the same and would be different from the past experience and practices.

New possibilities and aims would define the new advertising era and the industry has to update itself to convince and to remind to the people. It would become excessively important in the new world of trade and business enmity and opposition. In such an environment creating a valuable advertising message is very important and a must in the fast changing atmosphere in today's world. There is a dire need to generate new ideas and concepts in the field of advertising to survive and sustain.

Colours and various aspects of glamour have been brought in in the advertising industry and are there to stay and the industry would sustain.

As elsewhere in the world, advertising has taken a major position in Pakistan also. When came into being the country was very poor and weak financial system. In the subcontinent Muslims have a very small or almost no role and contribution in the financially viable life and hardly visible in advertising.

New country was shaped up primarily through agriculture alone as the country did not have any manufacturing, and transportation system etc at all when created.

Initial years of the new born country and the governments were utilized in creating basic facilities with an aim to ignite industrialization. A glance of the newspapers of that era shows that advertisements were generally and largely restricted to imported products and services available though on limited scale.

Television as a medium hit Pakistan's airwaves in 1964. And simultaneously advertisements for goods and services were also started on this medium. Publicising products and services through television advertisements are considered the most influential. TV advertisements are expensive as this mode was seen as the most powerful mass marketing and advertising layout. TV networks charge high for commercial airtime during popular television programming.

Geo News (was then Dubai based satellite channel, owned by Jang Group of Publications), ARY Digital (then UK based satellite channel owned by a Pakistani Haji Abdul Razzaq) are the famous and highest viewer ship. (Now the two big channels have shifted their operations in Pakistan and airing from Pakistan. In addition to these pioneers there were many more new news/entertainment channels were granted licence and were operating in the country. Major news channels operating in the country include Aaj, Express, Dunya and many more with some new entries in the offing)

Though did not replace print medium completely, television is considered most suitable medium for showcasing products. Print advertisements can explain the features of an exercise machine and advice the user as how to use it, radio advertisement can talk about them, whereas a television advertisement demonstrates how the machine works. Advertiser also enjoys and benefit from the reach of television with larger market coverage as well as reaching out to all age groups. With the growth television now reaches to most households in the country.

Advertising show shades of contemporary society. This mode (advertising) interacts with society and leave impact and impression on it in many ways. Advertising also get inspiration from the society and inspire society as well in return. Advertising has become a tool used to persuade while shaping up taste and act as opinion maker also.

Children and Advertisement

Children are the most vulnerable and sensitive target of media consumers. They easily get affected by media campaigns than adults. To be accurate the reason is that their simple and naive minds believe what they see on media and perceive from it.

UNESCO declared in 1999: "It is hardly an exaggeration to say that the most vulnerable individuals in this world of globalized media are our children. The changes we see at present and coming. Profoundly influence their live and circumstances. (Carlesson, Ulla and Feilitzen, Von Cecilia, 1999, P4)

It has been observed that children are more eager and enthusiastic users of the television medium. It is an established fact now that Children spend more time watching television than adults. The more they watch the television the more they get influenced and affected. Researchers have come across many theories of mass communication explaining the powerful impact and influence of such communication mediums, particularly television.

A Canadian scholar Marshal McLuhan earned international acknowledgment and recognition in 1960s when he came up with a profound understanding of electronic media, especially television, and its impact on society, culture and consumers.

McLuhan's theory, to be exact, was collection of lots of intriguing ideas gelled together by some common assumption.

Among those ideas the most focal were: "All media, from the Phonetic alphabet to the computer, are extension of man that cause deep and lasting changes in him and transforms his environment". (McLuhan, Marshall, 1962, pl3) McLuhan argued that changes in communication technology inviolably produce profound changes in both culture and social order.

To explain his vision and implication of spread of electronic media McLuhan used catchy and lasting phrases. He proclaimed that: "The medium is the message" (and the message). In other

words now forms of media transform (message) our experience of ourselves and their influence is ultimately more important to them than the content that is passed on in specific messages - technology determines experience. He used the term global village to refer to the new form of social organization that world inevitably emerge as instantaneous electronic media tied the entire world into the great social, political and cultural system. (McLuhan, Ibid) McLuhan pre-claimed as we understand media to be the "extensions of man His argument was that media quite literally expand imaginative and prescient, human hearing, and touch through time and space. Television as a media might open up a brand new vista for average human beings and enable us to be anywhere, everywhere immediately.

Even as studying the position and effect of television on kids viewing in a social truth, George Gerbner said: "The television set has entered in the family as a key member, the only one who tells maximum of number of events/stories most of the time". (Gerbner, G: 1971).

TV has a long term effect which can be minute, constant, and circumlocutory. However, the impact is cumulative and significant. (Gerbner, G, 1971, p263). Gerbner argues that: "Those who watch TV a lot are probably to be more inspired via the techniques wherein the world is framed through TV programming then are those who watch TV much less" (Gerbner and Gross, 1976).

Researchers like Gerbner have developed a theoretical framework and an empirical method for assessing the level of impact of TV violence on youngsters beliefs they widened the scope of their attraction to add not only the portrayal of violence but different styles of behaviour shown on television

UNESCO study on children and violence discussed the issue saying: "Important efforts are also required on the part of media - in form of, for instance, self regulation and production of an extensive output of television and radio programs and other media contents of high quality that fulfils children's various needs". (Carlsson, Ulla and Feilitzon, Von Cacilia, 1999).

Teenagers from a primary segment of the customers of many marketing and advertising companies lack ability to assess the content they were shown or made available to them. Youngsters lack the analytical skills and judgment of adults, marketing directed to children increases special worries. Kids are unable to assess the accuracy of the programming they were shown, and decide the difference in entertainment and marketing as the advertisers/marketers integrate the content and marketing seamlessly.

A commercial showing thumbs up for bungee jumping turned into stalked about whilst some children were see it as endorsement to emulate the stunt. Recently an advertisement show a younger girl had the candy and entering into the temper for straight talks tells her grandmother that she would like to attend on her so that her property might be bequeathed to their family. Such an advertisement can be cleverly smart and powerful, but they could send incorrect messages to young minds. Another example could be child stain from surf excel shows children soiling their clothes in such manner that can't prevent kids repeating the same.

Suggestive commercials that are seen by children, 'being teenager', had not been able to understand what they were seeing may create confusion in their minds. In brief, youngsters are impressionable consequently greater careful measures need to be taken as it is believed

in the developed international locations. It is expected that advertisers would:

- Bear in mind the expertise, sophistication, and maturity degrees of the Target market.
- No exposition the perceived resourceful class of the children.
- Pass on the knowledge and information with honesty and accuracy.
- Capitalize at the capability of advertising and marketing to influence social behavior in a positive way.
- To help built positive relationship between the child and parent.

A survey covering the children/teenagers in a developing society (media) a segment of advertising and marketing research and analysis exemplified advertising's growing recognition and cognizance on youngsters and their viewing choices. The data obtained through a survey of children in the age group of eight to 15 in 15 cities throughout the US indicates majority of children watch TV instead of interacting with books and reading.

According to the survey, a big (75 percent) child watched TV in almost all the cities covered in the sample. Moreover, youngsters were not found interested in watching movies or listening to the radio. Nearly ninety percent of 12 to 14 year age group youngsters were exposed to TV for at the least 4-6 hours a day. (Rao, Lula, UNESCO 1999)

In Pakistan, 69 percent of children on an average watch TV for four hours and timings for watching television most are from 4 to 8 pm. Children are generally keen in watching cartoons on television. On weekends, the survey say, 84 percent of youngsters watch television and they glued to TV screen between 8 to 12 pm. (www.Aftabassociate5.Com).

Advertisements are also used throughout programs aimed at targeting youngsters. As described in the code of ethics of the Council of Pakistan Newspaper Editors (CPNE), the media should prevent from the publication of news, articles, editorials, advertisements carrying immorality, obscenity, vulgarity or derogatory expression against, institutions or groups and glamorization of crime and incitements to violence. It also refer to US laws saying the content of advertisements has to comply with the laws of the USA and ethical requirements of decency and propriety. (Merrill 1989)

Media theorists and practitioners, in particular advertiser and advertising experts, fully aware and understand that whoever has the greater effect over the way of life and its symbols and signs and symptoms have the greatest impact on the development of the typification schemes people use to practice and their guidance with various social worlds.

It could be said that social establishments have the big impact in or manage over the social world as these institutions are able to dominate now typification schemes get created and used frequently. Why, as an example, is one emblem of a brand is extra sophisticated then all others? Are we less qualified to serve a less expensive indigenous brand to our guests? Why and what makes branded product carrying logo name or dresses with designer tag value higher than widely wide-spread alternatives?

To understand better take the example of airport security drill. If we travel frequently we know now how to pass through these security checks as we as individuals do not have much controlling options available to us during these checks. Under the changed security environment we reach to the airport early, though there might be a long wait.

As we reach, we do away with all metal objects from our wallet/pockets to our bags. We wear footwear that slips effortlessly. We keep our picture identity, passport and air ticket in easy access so that when we needed could reach them without hassle. However, despite all these precautionary measures, an alarm may go off as we go through the steel detector.

We are aware of what we should do once alarm goes off. We stop and allow ourselves to be scanned with an intrusive hand wand, if we manifest to travel on a day when safety is specifically tight, our carry-on bags can be opened and searched. We can be asked to turn on our digital system to make sure it is operational. In some situations, we might find this kind of treatment demeaning and humiliating. At the same time the advertisements and imparting persuasive messages to shape our attitudes towards the changed situation. For this the classified advertisements provide beneficial insights of the social world.

Goffman, in a book, *gender advertisements*, explains and argued insightfully concerning the impact advertising could have on users' perception of members of the opposite sex. He believes that classified ads are hyper ritualized representations of social motion using the sex appeal of women to draw the eye of fellow men could inadvertently teach or support social cues that might have inadvertent (Goffman, 1979).

Goffman mentioned how female frequently shown in advertisements as much less solemn and largely playful than men. They smile, pose and show their bodies in many advertisements in non-serious postures. They (women) put on playful clothing, and in numerous ways suggestively agreeing to take guidance from the men. Thus they are prone to sexual advances, and signal their preference for the men as these advertisements appeal to the eye of men. No wonder they are beneficial in positioning merchandise they are publicizing. But could these posturing of women be seen as teaching or reinforcing social cues that have consequences? Feminist theorists have also share and made similar arguments. (Walters, 1995)

We perhaps focusing and believing more than product definitions through these advertisements. We can be made to learn and believe a significant array of social cues, a few blatant, however, others pretty subtle. Once become known, those indicators could be utilized in routine to make observation of fellow participants (in daily life) of the same or opposite gender and to impose frames on them, their behaviour and actions, and the circumstances in which we come across them; or it is far feasible these commercials in reality strengthen the cues we have already found out in everyday life. The repetition of content material, However, lead us to give them greater significance or importance.

The worldwide bodies have also developed/created a framework for the advertisers. The International Chamber of Commerce (to which Pakistan is a member) for example has provided guidelines for the advertisers. Article 18 of ICC framework for responsible food and beverages gives specific guideline for marketing material or messages to teenagers.

The article says: "Marketing Communication should not exploit inexperience or credulity of children and young people" (www.iccwho.org).

It further suggests: "That having or using of the promoted product will give a teenager or young man or woman bodily, psychological or social advantages over children or younger human beings, or that not possessing the product could have the opposite effect. Marketing material should not undermine or tastes of parents, having regard to relevant social and cultural values" (ICC framework for accountable and beverage advertising and marketing

communication www.iccwho.org).

The National Food Alliances in Britain evaluated the results of commercials on kids and cited that 70 percent of all the advertisements have been promoting food items and over ninety eight percent of such classified ads have been for food with higher sugar, fat, salt and many other similar ingredients. In another study Hitchings conducted a small study of school children and indicated a relationship between the foods for which the children could remember the advertisements and the number of these food consumed. For individual food groups the contacts between foods remerged and food consumed was strongest for soft drinks and salty snacks. (Hitchings and Moynihan, 1998).

Television commercials have a massive effect on kids' food selection and eating behavior and it is able to impact more on the reality on their environment.

CONTENT ANALYSIS

While carrying out the research, data was collected on a sample of one hundred advertisements from around the world.

The researchers opted for random sampling as advertisements were not easily available. Multiple methods were used to acquire copies of these advertisements: direct recording from television as well as from discs.

Most of the advertisements were collected from DVDs and CDs randomly. Most of the advertisements were recorded from television channels in Pakistan. An advertisement table was prepared on the basis of categories such as "Product, Brand, Duration, Animation and Unreal Powers" to record the required information about the advertisements.

Each advertisement has been watched, six categories have been predefined on the basis of the products advertisements were made for. The advertisements were categorized to evaluate impact of those advertisements/products on children of various age groups. The broad categories covered in the analysis include snacks (cakes, biscuits, chips, noodles, jam, ketchup and wafers); sweets (candies, bubble gum, toffees, chocolates, and jellies); personal hygiene (toothpaste, soaps, mouth wash etc); soft drinks and juices; milk products and others (advertisements which do not fit into any category). The selection of advertisements was made from between 2012 to 2016 (universe of the study) and one hundred advertisements thoroughly studied and evaluated/analyzed to see the impact of advertisement on children.

The study was aimed at determining what types of advertisements were made for children in Pakistan and whether they suits society or not and to assess the impact of these advertisements on children. The research was aimed at analyzing the specific content (of the advertisements) and the effect of these advertisements on the eating habits of the children. It was also focused on children's perception of reality regarding these advertisements.

The main findings of the study are as follows:

- By and large, it is beyond the grasp of children under the age of eight to comprehend the intention behind TV advertising, which is to sway young minds. They, therefore, take the commercial message put out to them as true and correct.
- Candies, sweets, snacks and drinks are the most common products advertised to children.
- Children remember precisely the commercial gist of the products marketed to them and

they tend to be itching to buy the goods advertised.

- Commercials tend to whet the consumption appetite of children, so much so that they begin to nag their parents.
- Marketing of branded nutritionally negative food affects the eating choices the children make.
- Advertising leaves an indelible impact on children and moulds their habit of buying and eating. It also alters their view of what constitutes reality. It is therefore of utmost importance that the authorities keep a tab on what content the advertisements convey to the impressionable young minds. They should also, periodically, seek input from the target audience about the way such commercials impact them.

TARGET

The purpose of this research was to figure out what role the media plays in nurturing children and straightening their direction in keeping with the social, cultural and religious mores of Pakistan. So the chief idea behind this study was, firstly, to calibrate the impact of advertising on children and, secondly, to ascertain the changes the media is undergoing and whether or not this has affected the young ones in any way.

In addition to content analysis of advertisements, resource persons such as media students were interviewed to pull together information. This was done by way of distributing a questionnaire to 50 students. Information was also collected from journals, books, treaties, conventions, documents and the internet.

CONCLUSION

At 32 percent, sweets emerged as the most advertised product, so reveals our content analysis. This clearly militates against the PTV code on advertising standards, which reads: "Advertisements shall not encourage persistent sweet eating" (PTV Code of Advertising Standards and Practice, www.ptv.com.pk). At second place come snacks grabbing 30% of the advertising space covered in the sample. It is followed by the segment of personal hygiene with 15% advertising, milk products with 10%, soft drinks 8% and 'others' with 4% advertising. A majority of the adverts fell in the category of food products (noodles, ice cream, toffees, chips, lollypops, bubble gums and other junk stuff).

The effect of advertisements on food consumption of children especially junk food is very significant. In a study Hitchings showed the relationship between the foods for which children could remember the advertisements and the number of these foods consumed. (Hitchings and Moynihan, 1998). Hastings also reports that children's food preferences are being affected by the advertising of branded nutritionally positive food. (Hastings, 1998).

There is no denying the fact that media plays a key part in the lives of children, shaping their attitudes and preferences. Of course, what media does can overall be seen in positive light. Quite like the general audience, children also receive loads of information and knowledge from the media. Just how media leaves positive impact on its audience is acknowledged by all and sundry. But it is the negative aspect which one is afraid of. There is an urgent need to bridle the media in some way, preventing it from leaving a negative effect on children. They are not ready yet to make a judgment call, distinguishing between right and wrong, when aping their role model in the world of glitz.

Joseph Dominick stated that "advertisements, with the use of camera techniques and special effects, the product are made more appealing to children" (Dominick, 2002). Many studies have shown that children under eight cannot understand the intent of advertisement. The American Psychological Association has shown its concern that children below 8 years of age are vulnerable to advertising and that it should be restricted. (American Psychological Association www.epa.org)

Just how children accept negative effects of the media is clearly borne out from the way their mental attitudes change and their lifestyles suffer a decline. The young ones, supposed to spend their time studying, browsing books, doing workouts or engaging in social activity, today waste their time in front of the idiot box. Even a small child has easy access to the internet, which exposes them to unwanted things which they should not come in contact with and which they are not ready yet to comprehend in their young age. Therefore, the parents have a huge responsibility to shoulder to save their offspring from undesired things till they grow up.

Many researches have been carried out to find out the number of hours children spend watching television or using the internet. A survey about 12-year-old children in France and Switzerland by a newspaper journal of Geneva shows that they spend an average of three hours watching TV in front of their seats every day. Children in Germany watch less, while in USA children consume between four to five hours of television every day. (Dumont, 2001).

The children in Pakistan, living in urban areas, age 6-12 as described by Aftab Associates, watch television for 4 hours and the peak timing for watching are 4-8 pm. The children are mostly keen on watching cartoons. On weekdays 84% kids watch television and peak timings are from 8-12 pm (www.aftabassociates.com). The more kids stay glued to the TV sets, the more they will end up watching advertisements.

Positive and negative aspects are always attached to any concept or idea. This, therefore, is only fitting that we should know how to grab good things to one's life while rejecting the bad ones. That will prove to be an excellent way to survival in this world. With our planet turning into a global village, the inter-connectedness between nations has rapidly increased, the more so in economic and sociological spheres. Media are the best way to keep oneself posted on the sudden changes occurring in those areas as well.

With the development of new technology, the access to information found anywhere in the world becomes critical. Internet is the archetypal example of development of media underpinned by technology. Unfortunately some advertisers misuse the media. They dish out their creations, whether they be advertisements, films, reality shows, or music videos, based on sex and lust in order to lure the youth. To cast the children in the right shape is very essential and the advertisers should keep the ethical considerations in mind when disseminating their message to children.

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